

MIMS 2.1.2 - Business Circuit Theory

Aether Flow & Fortune hypothesis applied in an analog circuit model

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ABSTRACT

In the Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual philosophy, born out the Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology, an obvious postulate and analog emerges about business. Chiefly that it can be described using electrical circuit elements and diagrammatically organized and pre-planned. In the beginning this will be a touchy-feely circuit analysis, but as data emerges about the electro-chemical personality types, more precision will arise. The author discusses the role of the *A* power (Aether), and the other key aspects of the “Big G” diagram in the modulation of the behaviors of these circuits, while briefly discussing managerial strategies, tough-minded management et al., and even crypto-resiliency. Briefly issues of energy-mass and energy phase are considered in their *potential* implications in human circuitry analysis. A proposal for use of this theory in an emergency and disaster prevention mechanism for business is given.

Key Words: MIMS - business - Aether - physics - data analytics - operations research - management

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Aether Flow, Fortune, and MIMS Theory - a Primer

In MIMS 2.1.1-2 the author made several postulations² about the conjunction of æther (A power), and luck (or fortune), potentially money, etc.³ Inherent in that discussion was a general implication or even overt explication of the Law of Evolution's sub-law of Flux/flow, being inherent to the issue. Mimsically speaking, if the energy is flowing, then the Laws themselves support increased flux, albeit the alternation of laminar>turbulent>laminar would be effective. In follow up Financial Velocity papers⁴ there were discussions of the data leyline theory⁵, and evidence relating between the business cash flow and personal cryptocurrency, one of our identified MIMS from the MIMS 1.0 paper⁶. However, we also saw a potential standing wave in profits for the business in question. Study on that is ongoing. But, in the main, a postulate that finance and economics could be responding to some sort of data-æther - dæther - was postulated, and an entire crypto futures assessment looking at fibonacci pressure was used to make market swing predictions⁷. Therefore the "Big G" 'elemental' relationship between the A and N powers was proven. But what about the proposed inherent relationship of the A and P power, and also the F power?

In this paper the author wants to imply that **all MIMS can be treated as an electrical and/or geometric (Dougherty) circuit**. We must spend a little bit of time on circuit theory, on business as a MIMS, and then the playground opens up a bit more.

The audience should have a **firm** background in the previous MIMS material before continuing:

1. MIMS 1.0
2. MIMS 2.0
3. MIMS 2.1.1-2
4. Dæther⁸
5. Financial Addendum Series⁹

What is a Circuit?

In the words of R. Ashcroft, "A circuit is a construction." Well, it's a bit more than that, actually. It is a construction, to be sure, or rather a model with an engineering and mathematical

²

https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether

³ https://www.academia.edu/67387410/MIMS_2_1_212a_Fibonacci_Pressure

⁴

https://www.academia.edu/50902057/MIMS_2_5_1_Financial_Velocity_Addendum_A_Follow_up_on_Interesting_Developments_in_the_N_power

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/67983935/MIMS_2_1_212b_BTF_Addendum_and_Financial_Velocity

⁶

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/69663410/MIMS_2_1_212c_BTF_Addendum_and_Fibonacci_cycles

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/71652320/MIMS_2_1_212d_BTF_Reversal_manifested_as_predicted

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purpose. Math itself is already a tool (construct), used by scientists and engineers to describe physical processes and tools, etc. However, in the case of a circuit, the physical processes are well known and describable, but the type of diagram will depend upon the scale and function. In electronics, and in quantum electrodynamics, the diagrams are as depicted in the figures below.

AC VOLTAGE SOURCE

DC VOLTAGE SOURCE

Air Core Inductor Iron Core Inductor Ferrite Core Inductor Variable Core Inductor

The "Variac" variable autotransformer

Non-polarized

Polarized (top positive)

Variable

DIFFERENT TYPES OF DIODES

*LED, Small Signal, Zener,
 Schottky, Laser,
 Shockley, Tunnel,
 Avalanche*

Figures 1-9 (in order): voltage sources, $V=IR$, inductors, variacs, capacitors, transformer, diodes, feynman diagrams; credit: Google Image searches

In geometric-geology, they look different, as shown on the following pages. But regardless, the description is that of flow, inductance, resistance/conductance, capacitance, and other unique properties like transformation, hysteresis, reflection, etc. The resulting 'construction' is that of a model which describes the **overall circuitous relationship of source(s) and loads or elements**. In other words, potentiality (of energy source), current, and impedance (resistance) to that flow. So much as the circuit enables conductance through the physical matrix of the circuit, we can see theoretically 100% conveyance of energy. Except for superconductors, that doesn't happen.

Does the electronic energy flow like water¹⁰, or is it something else?¹¹ It is something else. The water flow (like a hose or pipe) analogy only gets us so far. In fact, electrons flow, if at all, upon the surface of the conductors, not in the center. So a braided cable is better than a solid wire. However, it can be said that quite possibly, the impedance is either the reluctance of the electron to adhesion with the atomic (elemental) cores, or the propensity to become stuck with a particular element. If that propensity is high, such as cloth, or rubber, then almost nothing will conduct. But it is **never true that the impedance is infinite or conductance impossible**, even outer space has permeability and a breakdown voltage. It was once thought to be rather high, but that number has been reduced owing to the more effervescent presence of baryonic cosmic dust, and ionic plasma. Therefore there is no free space, only varying degrees of conductance. Nevertheless, we will pretend for this paper that the regions outside the circuit

¹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VQsoG45Y_00

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bHlhgxav9LY>

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elements are equivalent to “no go zones” and represent infinite impedance, and only within the circuit diagrams themselves are there varying degrees of conductance (inverse of resistance). As such, a circuit focus is whittled down to:

- Connective (complete) relationship
- Sources
- Loads (elements)
- RLC parameters
- Function or behavior
 - Transforming
 - Digital vs. Analog
 - Receiver, transmitter, transceiver, etc.
 - Semiconductive
- Signals transducing and overall wave/pattern behaviors (such as modulation, construction, interference, etc.)

Figure 10 - Bruce Leybourne discusses Geometric Earthen Circuits at EU2016; credit: Leybourne/Thunderbolts Project¹²

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q355Haapq-0>

Figure 11 - Fractal Earth Channel's geometry diagrams; credit: FractalEarthChannel¹³

While not conclusive proof, there is something extremely compelling about the symmetries shown here in this earlier design.

¹³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kpt5VLIM_el

Figure 12 - FractalEarth explores the potential electric loops described by NASA in their geometric designs; credit: Fractal Earth Channel¹⁴

Elements of a Circuit

There are five main components of a circuit, and several secondary components. The five main components are:

1. Source
 - a. Voltage
 - i. Potential
 - ii. Tension
 - b. Current
2. Medium
3. Resistors
4. Inductors
5. Capacitors

The secondary components include:

6. Diodes/transistors
7. Switches
8. Transformers
9. Digital ICs
10. Antennas
11. [Superconductors]

Each of these will represent different aspects of a business' circuit. Therefore by ascribing their above-numbered positions, we can refer to them as their elemental type. By the time each of the business elements are here described and analogged, we can have a fairly decent logical arrangement for business engineering (visioneering, intrapreneuring, etc.):

1a - Voltage sources: Tension vs. potentiality in your business

A source of power in your business will be the 'charge' source, that is battery, which in most cases is the business owner themselves. However, tension in a business is built with dreams, expectations, and the vision management (purpose, mission, etc.) of the company. Many times the main problem with a business is either a) too high a tension/expectation, or b) too little potentiality, or some other leakage of charge (lack of focus, drive, motivation, etc.).

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dy-4Gbrez-E>

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So how much tension is too much? In reality it isn't possible to precisely indicate, because the *potentiality* of some businesses and projects is much greater than that of others. Also, it may be very true that the sudden potentiality creates a much greater *apparent* or synthetic/virtual tension than average situations. For example, the sudden potential of virtual reality projects may rival the average tension of social media projects. But as the current flows much more heavily for social media than for VR, it might very well be that the real potentiality and therefore tension in a social media company is artificially low. Conversely, it might also be higher, if the load is higher (for example an expected government infrastructure project with a high ROI out past 5 years).

So while we use 'voltage' in a rough way, it seems likely that the scalar value we will need, long term, will be a complex derivative of a multivariable function. That function has yet to be developed, to the author's knowledge¹⁵.

1b - Current sources

*"A Current Source is an active circuit element that is capable of supplying a constant current flow to a circuit regardless of the voltage developed across its terminals."*¹⁶

Current in business terms is almost exclusively about capital:

- Cash
- Credit
- Securities that are liquid enough to be exchanged
- Swaps
- Crypto
- Reserves (assets like gold bullion, etc.)
- Contracts

From this we can see that the more predictable, reliable, and strong a current source, the more likely it is able to supply that constant flow, regardless of the tensions in the business, market, economic, or management environments. Think of normal boom and bust cycles, even predictable ones, such as consumer shopping seasons and holidays (Black Friday, Christmas, etc.). There are, however, current sources which are predictably in need despite the tensions on the logistics supply chain (think: toilet paper, forks, lawn care services, security companies, funeral services, etc.)

The best, at least presently, currency source is government money, if one can get the contracts, and service those contracts by maintaining the relationships and access, all the better.

One of the more interesting currency sources would be the securities and swaps markets. In fact, there is a currency market itself, which is both transitory and also liquid enough to be speculative *and* a hedge. For making good predictions in that market, the author

¹⁵ The author's knowledge of Operations Research is rather rudimentary and basic, however.

¹⁶ <https://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/dccircuits/current-source.html>

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recommends looking into Jim Rickards' "COBRA" program¹⁷ and the "Strategic Intelligence"¹⁸ brand in general.

Regarding crypto and other hedge reserves, they should be treated as stocks and options. Both are potentially lucrative for the business, and also inherently risky or dangerous. It's difficult for a small or even medium business to put into these and expect enough return to be worth the management tension (and headache) resulting from these.

Note, for this paper, we will not use 'amps' for currency but \$, representing shifus (as well as dollars, of course).¹⁹

2 - the Medium

In most electronics the medium is either a copper wire, fiber, or the Force itself (signals through the air, such as radio waves). However, although this paper is mostly about the ætherial business issue (MIMS), the author should mention other mediums. Mostly these involve:

- ❖ Market(s) and marketplaces
- ❖ The internet
- ❖ Exchanges
- ❖ The SWIFT credit and banking system
- ❖ Direct marketing and crypto transactions
- ❖ Black Market ("off the record")
- ❖ Loans and other paper medium
- ❖ Increasingly: NFT (non-fungible tokens) which can be explained in a bit of detail in a moment
- ❖ Etc.

The purpose of mediums is to provide increased liquidity and decreased government regulatory influence. The problem with the government as a current source is that there is usually high impedance, and therefore a higher tension and breakdown voltage to attain that currency. Secondly, the government can also, depending on the situation, become an anti-MIMS and "reverse polarize" or "reverse transform" the business. Usually it is the opposite, with corrupt corporations sheisting the People (fleecing taxpayers) by 'greasing' the palms. However, increasingly the government is turning fascistic and wants, via influence from NGO lobbyists and the New World Order²⁰, to control businesses of all sizes²¹. For this reason the author has counteracted the ESG © score²² and introduced the FREETHtm score²³, however, its own algorithms have to be developed alongside the Operations Research that is AIM and SPACERS compliant. Nevertheless, let us assume the government is a *positive* transformer for the

¹⁷ <https://paradigm.press/publications/tac/>

¹⁸ <https://paradigm.press/publications/awn/>

¹⁹ This may seem vain of the author, but after all, this is novel. The formula for currency and power is, after all, proprietary and different, slightly, than in electrodynamical physics.

²⁰ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

²¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pquZ3BheelE>

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zbkCBllol2Q>

²³ <https://sites.google.com/view/star-enterprises-intrasite/spacers/freeth>

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purposes of the paper, and a government contract or grant is a net positive and its internal impedance²⁴ is *low to 0 (nil)*.

That leaves us therefore to deal with the medium's RLC characteristics. Mainly, though, we are dealing with the æther/dæther (hereafter: A power) as a medium in MIMS discussion, which has the following hypothesized characteristics:

- $V=0$, $R=\text{infinite}$
- $V > \text{avg}$, $R = \text{high}$, assume $> 1\text{M}\Omega$ if I (current) $< \text{avg}$ \$
- $V < \text{avg}$, $R = \text{low}$, assume $< 100\text{k}\Omega$ if $I > \text{avg}$ \$
- L (inductance) will be less impedance and more (re)storative to currency *if* the current is stable through cycles, and low frequency (mostly consumables, etc.
 - If f is high, there will be an inherent 'resistance' to the change in the inductance, in electronics, because of the coils, and this is continued to be assumed in business, but that may not be an ironclad rule is the point
- C (capacitance) is, in the case of business a literal 'bridging the gap' between these planar elements:
 - Supplier, Consumer
 - Talent, Management
 - Opportunity, Investment
 - Return, Risk
 - Market, Advertising
 - Design, Engineering
 - Etc.
 - It follows that the greater the company capacitance, the greater the tension or potential, and also the greater the return current.
 - If f is high, then the capacitance is driven to 0, and this is bad in a company, so they will need to add more capacitive elements to the company, leading to some very bad habits. This will be covered in more detail in management.
 - If f drives to 0, then the company loses its capacity to do business as impedance/resistance skyrockets to the company's ability to adjust to the market demands

It goes without saying that since we do not know the anatomy of the Aether, and have only proposed a "dæther", that all the discussion of these parameters fall into the category of metaphysics²⁵. Be that as it may, computer models should still be possible.

²⁴ Yes sources have RLC characteristics, and in fact once hooked to the analog circuit will have an impact. BUT in electronics design we tend to ignore these, unless we deal with very high (relatively) values such as power plant generators, nuclear, etc. What is more pertinent will be the hysteresis of the system.

²⁵ Which is why this is a MIMS paper, not EPEMC specifically. It's a [business] philosophy paper.

3 - Resistors

In any circuit, impedance is determined by general blockage or resistance to flux. However in this mimsical discussion we are confining, or rather defining, “resistors” as elements of a business circuit to be:

- Individuals that perform the act of resisting adaptation, adoption, evolution, or progress - Change - actively or passively.
- Circumstances, groups, or even projects which impede the progressive²⁶ flow, current or other (talent, brainstorming, etc.), and therefore perform a relative drain on the business.
 - ◆ Bear in mind: resistance itself can be a very good thing: most people’s ideas are bad/unscientific and should naturally be resisted.

The issue for management or a board to decide is how to adjust the voltages, currency, and if possible arrangement of elements to eliminate *negative* resistance, which is what we presume here. Note that the ohms of impedance are inverse to the om (zen flow state) of a harmonious business! Pure coincidence of phonics or EPEMC related archetypes?

4 - Inductors

An inductor is a “manifestor” and they are naturals at inducing or instigating action. In other words, they are capable of altering the electro-chemical behaviors of people, places, and things which affect the business. They are “movers and shakers.” They are relatives, mentally speaking, to Transformers, which use inductance.

To induce usually means to entice, cajole, inspire, or exhale life into some project, object, or target (like an M&A acquisition, or real estate sale, etc.). It requires currency to occur, although by mimsical theory spiritual construction could induce action in others without \$\$\$. But, setting aside the “Field of Dreams” (build it and they will come), most projects by far require capital injections to achieve anything. Granted that no one can tell how much spiritual investment even a small mom-n-pop kiosk or business might take as compared to real overhead, it can be assumed as per the axiom of cosmic potential²⁷ that more æther goes in that capital injection. Even in a large project there will be a larger number of interested parties trying to achieve ‘synergy’ and keep a thing going. Grave resistances do appear for many things in the world of entrepreneurship, or else multi-level marketing would work as a business for everyone. The simple fact is that most people do not possess the potential, in terms of charged charm and wit or talent, nor the capital currency for sustaining the source of a fledgling business. That’s why they fail. Yes, MLM’s can start up for around \$300, but realistically it will be thousands to tens of thousands just to meet the bare minimum need. It is the author’s recommendation that no new business is started with anything less than \$20,000 present (2022) capital requirements, and the more the better. A \$2,000 unexpected loss/shrinkage representing 10% of capital reserves is often too frightening for most people to consider when they begin a

²⁶ Not here used as a political term but in real value of making forward progress. Progressivism is highly regressive and high in resistance, based on current results.

²⁷ As mentioned in The Cosmic Rearrangement paper, most systems, if not all, where energy flows down from a higher source: the vast majority of the energy is retained in the source, rather than the load, for it to work. This is true of Car batteries to the Void & Aether, Aether & material (measured Universe), etc.

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new dream in earnest. If that's the case, then the MIMS is too risky for the capacitance of the individual entrepreneur/owner wannabe. It is unsustainable in its low potential (no Power).

There is a related property which must be discussed in relation to induction and that is hysteresis, the electrical equivalent of inertia. Obviously everyone understands that they can have inertia (mostly to change and newness) in business and life. But while most people focus on the momentum aspect, hoping that keeping going like a full back through every problem will sustain the dream, few understand the less mechanical meaning: **systemic memory**.

The world *knows you* and *your career/talents* as X, Y, and Z. If you learn to, you can trick the system, but only for so long. Long ago Earl Nightingale did an episode of "Lead the Field" titled "One Thing You Can't Hide." That one thing was your vocabulary, diction, (even upbringing/class) and how you spoke in a business environment. This little understood and less honestly admitted fact is that people's IQ, EQ, and grasp of the English (or other) language will determine, for the most part, their role in society according to others. There is a talent limit known as a "competency ceiling"²⁸ however, few ever even get the chance to reach such a limit because what stops them are doors which [they] close beforehand. It might be as simple as a tendency to whine, complain, or have low self-esteem or appear to lack confidence. It might be as glaring as they are jerks and cursing in inappropriate situations. Once people lose faith and trust in your abilities, it is difficult to get it back, and easy for people to spread rumors, ruin reputations, and for all of this to become part of a *systemic dossier* on you. They want to make that official with an ESG²⁹, and believe the author when he says they intend to use your social media presence³⁰ and popularity as some sick/twisted measure of your worth³¹. They think your behavior is 100% quantifiable and tied to your credit and net worth. Businessmen in general often "size up" people as capable and likely to succeed, vs. "not going anywhere." This is despite the fact that:

→ Past trends are no indication of future events, only rough estimations!

If one could look at a person and *know* if they were a "born loser" then clearly no "losers" would ever get married or breed. But social media is encouraging the opposite: shallow and short lived hookups often with "all the wrong people." That retrains everyone who is not a manipulative, shallow social hacker/engineer³² (manipulator or narcissist), to become a modern loser. What a shame. Think of poor Van Gogh: a "born loser"³³. Or Mozart³⁴ and many others besides!

²⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Peter_principle

²⁹

<https://www.heartland.org/publications-resources/publications/financial-institutions-are-expanding-esg-social-credit-scores-to-target-individuals-small-businesses>

³⁰

<https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Business%20Functions/Strategy%20and%20Corporate%20Finance/Our%20Insights/Five%20ways%20that%20ESG%20creates%20value/Five-ways-that-ESG-creates-value.ashx>

³¹ <https://theimpactinvestor.com/calculate-individual-esg-score/>

³²

<https://theconversation.com/dark-empaths-how-dangerous-are-psychopaths-and-narcissists-with-empathy-178715>

³³ <https://inc42.com/buzz/lessons-historys-persistent-loser-vincent-van-gogh/>

³⁴ <https://www.grunge.com/412714/mozart-died-penniless-heres-why/>

5 - Capacitors

Capacitors are high impedance individuals who **do not bridge gaps but create them** by opening large numbers of projects which require others to close the gap with potential talent, financial investment, manpower, etc. They are little appreciated, in that they appear to do nothing. But in reality these “dreamers” are known for some of the greatest achievements in mankind’s history, and certainly can be well worth their funding in an organization. One of the most stupid decisions middle management makes, unbeknownst to the upper management, executives, or board (all of which are decaying in quality, backbone, and wisdom in the gig economy “of things”), is to cut loose “deadweight” talent which isn’t dead weight at all.

The most famous loss of a high capacitance element (a transformer overall, but still) is when Thomas Edison (a famous transistor-transformer) refused to pay Nikola Tesla the \$100,000 he owed him for fixing a problem³⁵. When he did so, he doomed himself to the victimhood of the banks, and to lose General Electric (then Edison Electric) and all its assets in one fell swoop³⁶. He failed to see the capacitance in another person, probably being jealous, and therefore increased the impedance in his own circuit as he leveled the cycles of sales and cash flow³⁷. What a shame for Mr. Edison,³⁸ and for Mr. Tesla. Both men were underappreciated in the long term!

Increasing the cyclical work and cash flow (R&D budget) of capacitive elements, such as talented inventors, engineers, artists, and program directors, may drive impedance down and certainly can increase the Potential reservoirs of the business.

Remember: keeping a capacitor, even if they cannot function great, might be a way to keep a serious competitor from taking off.

6 - Transistors

A transistor is a semiconducting element. These diodic elements³⁹ only flow when they have *enough potential*. Ergo, they are not only interns that lack training and development, but anyone that *could shine* if they were “turned on.” Mr. Edison, again an owner and inventor himself, was able to shine *after* he overcame the “breakdown voltage”⁴⁰ of mimsical tests to find the working conditions for the incandescent light bulb⁴¹, a most famous story of American ingenuity. However, other transistors often include musicians, movie directors, writers, social media influencers, etc. who simply need either time, capital injection, or just exposure to wider audiences to “pop.” The market is not as picky on this as people think. Many current sources, such as venture capitalists and investment bankers, think of businesses as blue chip⁴² vs.

³⁵ <https://tecreview.tec.mx/2020/03/16/en/who-stole-from-whom-thomas-edison-vs-nikola-tesla/>

³⁶

<https://www.loc.gov/collections/edison-company-motion-pictures-and-sound-recordings/articles-and-essays/biography/life-of-thomas-alva-edison/>

³⁷ <https://www.businessinsider.com/thomas-edison-in-the-obstacle-is-the-way-2014-5>

³⁸

<https://www.ge.com/news/reports/ghost-in-the-machine-edison-lost-currents-war-but-won-a-bigger-prize-that-still-helps-keep>

³⁹ The differences between mosfets, diodes, and BJTs is beyond pedantic for this type of paper.

⁴⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Breakdown_voltage

⁴¹ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

⁴² <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/bluechipstock.asp>

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non-blue chip. This is a mistake. In fact most semiconductor or high tech companies have tight margins while businesses like trailer parks, home health, funerals, e-commerce, etc. have high margins and few if any can predict likely success. For example Dr. Jordan Peterson was just an average professor who sounded like Kermit the Frog and said nothing controversial in psychiatry, until circumstances and a tough skin/firm backbone cast him into the spotlight. Then his element burned so hot he exceeded his capacitance and had a health crisis⁴³. After recovery he has been, shockingly, able to resume his fame and career, though not at the same heat and intensity, but with a new level of elemental importance in the marketplace. He sells books and tickets, and people click his videos. They want to hear what potentially life saving/altering advice he can provide. There is a market for “fresh” (refreshing honesty in 2022 seems fresh to young people) ideas which captivate minds. This is potential. Once “turned on” Dr. Peterson has been in a steady state of LED high glow⁴⁴. If he had been a resistor like an incandescent bulb, or had a short fuse like some, he would have just popped⁴⁵, and never recovered. The music industry is full of one hit wonders that have struggled with this issue!

7 - Switches

Switches, by contrast, turn others on. Joe Rogan is one of the hottest switches in the business market now.⁴⁶ People from Hollywood to tech to policy and governance all want to go onto his show and get audiences “turned on” to what they are selling. Similarly Patrick Bet David switches people onto new business ideas⁴⁷, and to unusually good (high quality) interviews with infamous personalities (like mob bosses⁴⁸, or cranks like John McAfee⁴⁹). These switches often themselves can be on again/off again, or have strange RLC behaviors that don’t enable them to be particularly good at anything pragmatic. But they are masters of turning on others. If Joe Rogan had never been discovered, he’d be just another mostly funny drug and martial arts addict. But the fact is that he *is* a success, from comedy to TV to MMA to his podcast. He is in a good position to switch on the altstream⁵⁰, and has done so, much to the chagrin of the mainstream, which imagines only itself can/should have the right to control who gets famous, and why.

- The mainstream chose the Red Sweater guy as a political darling, based on looks alone, and found out he was less than desirable based on his social media publishings⁵¹
- Joe Rogan chooses to interview people like Jimmy (Bright Insight) and Randall Carlson, as well as famous and infamous comedians and actors, directors and science whizzes, and he makes their names into household brands.

⁴³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J0CJiWxeaFc>

⁴⁴ 1.2M views (as of 4/7/22): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lwJ9gY6mCc8>

⁴⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3ktjZih3LQ>

⁴⁶

<https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2022/2/17/the-podcast-about-joe-roigans-podcast-is-hugely-popular>

⁴⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/c/VALUETAINMENT>

⁴⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vzYwCmDDSLA&list=PLFa0bDwXvBICRNOFtfmvq_dzMkNBTI5m6

⁴⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WBgFGwJA1D0>

⁵⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RxmW9eizOAo>

⁵¹

<https://www.thedailybeast.com/ken-bones-disturbing-reddit-history-shows-hes-not-nearly-as-adorable-as-we-thought>

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Controlling switches⁵² in your business is **absolutely vital to succeeding in any competitive environment**. Learn to switch on the positive elements, and switch off (or even fire/defuse) the rest.

Special cases:

- ❖ Circuit breakers - a circuit breaker is usually a 'metal type' personality, (ENTJ⁵³) which has no qualms about behaving coldly to anyone. Also this could be controls in the business, performance or cost related with hard consequences for failures. You need controls to manage a business. Do not ostracize individuals with the gift of "cutting through bullshit"
- ❖ Fuses - these people are usually 'wood type' (type A⁵⁴) connector people, fed by ego, praise, recognition etc. But they help switch on situations, until they blow up. Then nothing works. They are only used now in very high voltage and high current applications. Therefore Dan Peña, or Jack Welch, or Steve Jobs type people are only acceptable if they a) perform and b) at a high level. Otherwise they are not worth the trouble and can absolutely sabotage a business circuit. The downfall of big egos has killed many companies or popular bands.
- ❖ Toggles - A toggle switch is an extremely cool, alluring type of switch with a noticeable click. You want these for salesmen. When they switch on, your sales will be stupendous.
- ❖ Potentiometers - This is a variable switch, much like a transistor. However, the key is they provide potential to your business circuit. Dr. Peterson has little potential, while Patrick Bet David has enormous variable potential. Do not assume those in your management structure always need "turning up." That isn't how to properly *tune* the circuit. Much as a good switch might hate to be hampered, if you can control their control, you can avoid losing their talents elsewhere (always a potential headache) and empower them to do something excellent. Consider this in the areas of HR and recruitment.
- ❖ Variac Sources - A variac is a variable voltage source. While there isn't much indication that individuals can't turn on/off or up/down their potential, it is a management criterion to control the creative output and R&D budgets so as to adjust focus in a company. Therefore this element mostly falls under the category of management controls/mechanisms, especially project management. Through the science of Operations Research, and Data Analytics specifically, one can control the potential tension in a company's operation.

8 - Transformers

A transformer adjusts tension and current via a) induction and b) magnetic attraction-flow. Magnetic attraction is gathering talent. Moving talent around (activity to activity, department to department, relationship to relationship, etc.) enables a transformer to do 'magic'

⁵² And "routers", which most people call "connectors"

⁵³ <https://www.16personalities.com/entj-personality>

⁵⁴ <https://www.webmd.com/balance/what-is-a-type-a-personality>

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for the company. It requires a cyclical source of projects, talent, and currency. The currency is “stepped up” if the tension is brought down, and vice versa. However, a true transformer can increase tension (and his/her own potential) at will, and can thereby enhance (with linear effort) the currency \$\$ flux. However, they are hot elements, require lubricating (usually bonuses, perks, etc.) and can yet **explode**. Worse, they can reverse a circuit and might be a vengeful group, so beware.

In terms of non-human elements, transformers tend to be software suites for managing a business, like sales tracking, point-of-sales, client management services, software-as-a-service, enterprise software, etc. When these are used, the transformer can easily become the heart/core of the business and its own bottleneck, without which there will be no cyclical frequency of sales and cash flow, and no “alternating currency” with which to cover debt-service. This is a vulnerability because certain credits are callable at any time, and certain debts are targets for acquisition if banks sell to bidders on the debt.

9 - “digital” Integrated Circuits

It’s only natural to want to package up portions of a business and offer them as ‘black box’ connectors (leased, contracted, licensed, etc.). And by extension, in a gig economy, virtual executives and advisors are like this. They all want to pretend they are not one-size-fits all, and they will market themselves as transformers, but inside such integrated circuits are complex apparati (usually a wealth of experience and personal/proprietary connections). If there is a transformation, it’s designed to fit a certain scenario. This either limits them in expansion of utility, or broadens them, but with a cost of profundity and market depth. Regardless, the predictability of service, and of quality, is desirable, and the “digital” outcome matches our digital world greatly. A perfect example of an IC in a business would be a cloud service or IT manager. On the outside, these appear cookie cutter, but in reality who they are connected to, and what they can do is a large determination of the results of predictability.

10 - Antennas

An antenna is a medium, usually a wire or coil of copper, which is able to receive special information. The antenna is set to match the frequency or band of frequencies. Such an element in business is useful for gathering intel (on competitors and the marketplace), and for sending information signals. Again, this is a quality greatly desired in salesmen. As an antenna is a quarter-length (wavelength) device⁵⁵, do not devote more than ~ ¼ of your budget to salesmen’s commissions alone, or to your marketing department, or they will control the fate of the business!

11 - Superconductors

Superconductors are highly researched elements, which are not currently widely used. They have zero resistivity, in their operating temperatures, and have magical-like magnetic levitation properties. And they are *expensive*. Therefore, be prepared to pay a premium price to

⁵⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electrical_length

have an Elon Musk on your board or in your team. Other than that, perhaps little can be said at this time. We will see what mimsy, if any, is enabled as we discuss these elements further in.

Chinese 5 “Element” Theory, the Phases of Energy in motion

Before moving into MIMS business, let us recall from a previous EPEMC paper comparing cosmology to the Chinese Sciences, that we learned the Chinese did not see ‘elements’ but phases of energy in transition. That is, they rightly and naturally recognized (second only to the original Egyptians⁵⁶) that matter transitioned between solid, liquid, and gas states because of **energy quantity**. They took no steps, and certainly no rigorous mathematical steps to quantify this quantity. They preferred to deal with it in terms of the polarity, and particularly the hot / cold and excess / deficient polar relationships. They did, however, recognize field relationships and the influence of energetics upon moving and living systems.

In particular we want to hone in on the two polar hearts of the alchemical relationship, which can be related in the following compass manner:

Figure 13 - Compass of Five Phases, with Earth at the center; credit: author

⁵⁶ Atlantians?

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From this perspective we can see that fire and water are not only hot and cold, liquid vs. plasma, but matters of above and below. That is important in a management discussion. But in the elements of a circuit we mentioned metal and wood types. This, we can see, are the two energetic formations of East and West, which in Spanish are Este and Oeste. The polarity of these is metaphysical. Almost arbitrary, but not irrelevant. Wood formations are creative, organizational, tendril like, and growth-dependent. Both need stretching but Wood craves stretching, but not too much, while Metal resists it. Metal, by contrast, is regulatory, firm, blunt, hard, sharp, incisive (while wood is decisive), and potentially cold or even brutal. This is electricity, but it is also the Executive type role. You want these people running your organization, and indeed in the 5 Phases, Metal dominates Wood (chops). So we see that there are needs for control, discipline, and even harsh or brutal methods. But the fast fact is that it doesn't make Metal more important. Woods wouldn't imagine so, anyways. They are inherently narcissistic or egotistical, while metals are inherently depressive, bipolar, autistic, or genius.

PEMC - Energy-mass

Another important short discussion is to recall that light is a circuit, not a mass (as in a particle), and it has no momentum⁵⁷. However, mass not being fundamentally particulate, but electrical is a well known issue, in that all "masses" of particles are measured in electronVolts. But, what interests us is to recall that these circuit diagrams - Feynman diagrams - have different behavioral symbology than RLC analog circuits. That's likely because the light exchanges are themselves closed loops (counter-rotating Bessel functions, described in Scott-Dougherty models) which have *intrinsic RLC properties*. We call these properties reflection, diffraction, refraction, and absorption. A perfect reflector cannot perform any work, according to mass spectroscopist Pierre-Marie Robitaille⁵⁸, who showed the failure of Kirchoff's Gas Law⁵⁹. This is ironic because Kirchoff also came up with the circuit laws⁶⁰ which led to $V=IR$. However, the fact of the matter is that the circuits have a different form at different scales. Thus we expect a macroscopic variation of electrical circuit behavior.

What does this teach us about business? All businesses need and require flow, and have circuit parameters. However, at different scales the energy-mass (probably via the A power, not F or P powers) dictates differing behaviors. This is very important for the entire circulatory behavior of the business.

- One size fits all business guru books won't work
- You're not a failure in your business if you try high level stuff but it doesn't work on your scale or level.
- Learn the physics (P power) of the business circuit behaviors at your scale/level; and make adjustments.
- Be careful not to let your mind's eye get myopic and ignore the **zoom** (scale again) or lens with which you view situations.

⁵⁷ Claims by SM that it does are disregarding the biefeld-brown effect and the solar electric force (wind) field.

⁵⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c-Luq0fOJK8>

⁵⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DodFojdkSIA>

⁶⁰ https://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/dccircuits/dcp_4.html

Business as a MIMS

Let us recall that a MIMS is first and foremost a membranous structure/construction in for a relationship between **wants/desires/ambitions and physical reality**. The meaning of this is that *anything that improves the physical reality for the ambitious is acting as a MIMS*. Most entrepreneurs from the Vanderbilts to the Elon Musks get into this game to make their own and their family's lives better. Why else do it? Wage earning existence is drudgery and near to slavery (because of illegal income taxes⁶¹ imposed at the end of an FBI barrel⁶² and IRS audit⁶³), but that doesn't mean business is much easier. 1,001 factors influence and impede the success of the swarthy entrepreneur, up to and including failure, bankruptcy, jail, failure, disgrace, and even suicide. Sometimes people cannot hack it. Mostly we see this among the youths high is socialist installed "Dunning-Krugerism"⁶⁴ (because they received participation trophies instead of real ones), but also it sometimes follows those with a "failure gene" or "unlucky bone." But you're only a failure if you give up and walk with a "Loser's Limp."⁶⁵ That is another subject, entirely.

A MIMS should, by design, lead to an improvement in one's life. If it does not:

★ Check your premises

Recently, the author was "taken in" to what turned out to be a ponzi crypto scheme, couched as a proof-of-stake legit financial contract. The author had trusted the due diligence of a fairly expert⁶⁶ cryptocurrency tech analyst, and several in the AIMtm think tank had this issue. In fact, over 2,000 people were robbed in this highly illegal manner⁶⁷, and the creators of the MATIC-fomo continue to defraud people with new and fake tokens⁶⁸. It's unfortunate because proof-of-stake might be a good investment, but the pools have simply not worked out. In this case, though, the entire principal was lost when the MATIC-fomo 'creators' locked the contract and absconded with the cash to create a "V2." They are, in the end, new digital comen. The author deleted the steps for Maticfomo from the crypto howto guide, and thankfully no one else will be hurt. However, the money that was for useful projects was gone. This is an anti-MIMS, as one would expect a ponzi scheme. Frequently the scams in business only benefit the scammers in the short term as by far most of the white collar criminals get caught eventually, when they mess up.

For the conned, it is automatically an anti-MIMS.

So we must be careful, in discussing business, to avoid known anti-MIMS like "vulture capitalism" and various pyramid schemes. It's one thing if the MLM company, for example, works. It's another if it destroys families, as the author has seen happen before. This, or great

⁶¹

<https://taxfoundation.org/today-history-income-tax-ruled-unconstitutional-pollock-v-farmers-loan-trust-co/>

⁶²

<https://www.fbi.gov/kansascity/press-releases/2013/liberty-couple-charged-in-2.8-million-embezzlement-heck-kiting-scheme-to-fund-gambling-lavish-spending>

⁶³ <https://turbotax.intuit.com/tax-tips/general/what-does-it-mean-that-taxes-are-voluntary/L5cjhVIhh>

⁶⁴ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Dunning-Kruger-effect>

⁶⁵ <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=loser%27s%20limp>

⁶⁶ le, a crypto mining engineer

⁶⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W_4DZJ5MRRw

⁶⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h2EmEwg9HWO>

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scandals like Enron, or WeWork, WorldComm, etc. are all examples. So are NINJ loans⁶⁹ and the mortgage bubble and collapse, which made some people rich, cost millions their homes and nearly ended the world economy.

Therefore, let us be clear: when we discuss business as a MIMS, it does not have to be a mom-n-pop capitalist business. It could be a giant sheisty non-profit like Red Cross. But it cannot ever be a company which directly destroys lives, for that would be an anti-MIMS.

How can we know the good from the bad? One knows based on the design and integrity of the company. If they have no integrity, and a history of fraud and even conviction, there's more than likely something anti-mimsical going on in this business which is nothing short of a **crime** and **immoral and unethical**, both.

- ❖ Nothing in this paper should be construed as condoning fraud, embezzlement, monopolies, or illegal loopholes, laundering, racketeering, etc.
 - There are legal tax loopholes, and these are MIMS, for heavy taxes are anti-mimsical to any business.

Management as a MIMS

Everything that **is**, especially that which is organized, requires human management if it is not controlled by Mother Nature. Therefore, shouldn't it be true - wouldn't it be ideal if - management was a MIMS and not a toxic environment for the workers, and the executives, too. Wouldn't the Board be happiest if it guided the management's hands towards a healthy "productivity climate" that used tough (but fair) minded management, enabling the workers to be guided and developed, instead of disillusioned and micromanaged?

Therefore, we must remind the audience what the hypotheticals of a MIMS should consist of:

- Receptive above, solid below (foundational), see the original MIMS diagram⁷⁰
- Infinite potential, finite modeling (and conforms to scientific method)⁷¹
- Capable of rigorous testing and improvement
- Promotes **lots of ideas**, while eliminating most of them
- Promotes life and "essence" (in the American Dream, we call this 'the good life')
- Ethical rather than morally focused⁷²
- Utilizes data and the Power of Numbers
- Utilizes evidence and fact, and the Power of Physics/Principles
- Conforms to the Force (F power), even using it⁷³
- Without getting religious: God/Lord approved ("tianyì" in Chinese, 'Heaven's Will')

⁶⁹ No income, No job

⁷⁰ MIMS 1.0 p.10

⁷¹ MIMS 2.0 p.5

⁷² https://www.academia.edu/66889409/MIMS_4_01_Morality_as_a_Simulation_of_Holiness

⁷³ Such as cryptocurrency mining

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These things enable any MIMS, according to the research, to exist and improve lives. Therefore we seek a management system that does the above things. The author has only found three main systems which do these things and promote a Productivity Climate, consistently, and prompt them:

- ❖ Tough-Minded Management
- ❖ Rockefeller Habits
- ❖ The Midas Touch

Figure 14 - The Productivity Climate, from the author's new Resilient Way: A New Wave short business plan (proprietary); credit: author/J. Batten

Anyone of these is compatible with all the micro-systems promoted anywhere by black belt whatevers, and experts. What is harder to see, is how to promote them when there is an active agenda by certain corporate elites to promote anti-MIMS like socialism⁷⁴, equity/diversity quotas⁷⁵, racism (calling it anti-racism)⁷⁶, and other 'entitlements' which rob people of their work ethic and rob entrepreneurs of their incentives, to fill the bellies of moochers⁷⁷ and losers⁷⁸. That is not easy to figure out. The old saying, "one rotten apple can spoil the whole bunch" definitely applies.

What does Mr. Batton advise? One should read the entire book, but the author's [summary notes are accessible here](#).⁷⁹ Needless to say there is a strong implication of the importance of:

- Physical health
- Mental support
- Responsibility

⁷⁴

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

⁷⁵ These are actually illegal under the Civil Rights Act of 1964

⁷⁶ To be more blunt, Critical Race Theories and all similar are anti-white racism. They are, also, anti Asian.

⁷⁷ To borrow Ayn Rand's terms.

⁷⁸ As in, physically unfit, incapable of accomplishment, inventive of unreal sciences and 'studies' which have no productive quality, and which drain funds and inflate egos. The right calls these people "betas" and "thetas." As a Libertarian the author prefers to use the more harsh term: POS's.

⁷⁹ <https://www.amazon.com/Tough-Minded-Management-Joe-D-Batten/dp/1592441181>

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- Fairness
- Development over training
- Operations Research
- Honesty
- Free-market capitalism and not socialism
- Work as its own form of luxury
- Patriotism
- Serving others
- Paying what's due to the investors and consumers
- Not passing the buck
- Not being a “yes man”
- Etc.

- Expectations Work, Ladies and Gentlemen.
- Power = Work over Time⁸⁰

In other words, being a true person, and not a lazy shill. That isn't so hard, if one has scruples and denies the need for instant gratification⁸¹ which lures one into the ideas of conning others out of their wealth for one's own easy benefit⁸².

Nevertheless, we see some strong implications therein, whether we consider them from a Zheng Qi perspective, or electro-dynamical (electronic elements), or a spiritual perspective. The spiritual is easy:

- ★ God, country, family
 - “Praise the Lord and pass the ammunition!” ~Dan Peña⁸³

In terms of Zheng Qi, we know there is a strong EPEMC connection because of the meaning of Zheng (upright) tying back to the cosmic pole, and tangentially to Te/De (inner power). Internal locus of control is key to being able to take responsibility for failure, and to manage others. Righteousness does not have to be about morality, albeit most righteously ethical people **are moral** at their start.

While vulture capitalism does encourage “thieves and brigands” we see from the previously cited scandals, or from Bernie Madoff et al. that there are reasons, still, to not be a compulsive liar and thief.

There are, despite declining numbers of people worshipping “the Lord” worldwide, plenty of ethical and incidentally-moral people (even some of them are atheist). What there seems to be a dearth of is a backbone to say what needs to be said, regardless of the fear generated by the anti-MIMS of social media which incites mobs and ‘cancel culture’⁸⁴. So we will, in this paper, promote the factual idea that inner strength and character matters most in tough-minded

⁸⁰ (or Tension amplified by Currency)

⁸¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Yo4WF3cSd9Q>

⁸² Socialism to a T.

⁸³ At one point in history the wealthiest Hispanic on the planet as CEO of Great Western Oil. He started the company with \$700 he borrowed because he'd lost everything despite making hundreds of thousands in the stock market game. This is an alpha.

⁸⁴ Or as the author prefers to call it: “cancer culture”

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management. Not what you say, but what you do. And that means courage, loyalty, honor, patience, and the rest of the virtues. In this way, we can fulfill the remainder of the “Big G” diagram’s requirements, and therefore fulfill at least that portion of the MIMS requirements.

As for making a system of infinite potential, modeled with finite truth and data, that is really up to the visioneer for the company, but certain “[Rockefeller Habits](#)” like the forms of meetings⁸⁵ and organizational tools⁸⁶ might improve the chances.

How will this appear in electronics? It will be necessary for the reader to connect what has been said about “tough-minded management” here, and the MIMS to the previous section on elements, to understand that **putting the right people in the right places is absolutely key to management behaving as a MIMS** and not an anti-MIMS (toxic work environment).

>>where in that statement is there any room for gender, race, or other prejudices?<<

Regarding Creative Briefs, by Macon Asbury

“A Creative Brief is a specific roadmap between Client and Provider of Services so that there are no misunderstandings. It enables collaboration and teamwork among all stakeholders involved.

A CB has 4 elements The first is

- *WHAT -This asks what we are proposing or doing. How is it defined? It could be a sentence or a paragraph.*
- *WHO - who is the audience, this enables conversations beyond the obvious and helps clarify anything that might be in a clients mind.*
- *WHY - This explains the reason behind the idea. It summarizes the meaning of the job. This allows a passionate response should there be one. Why is this idea compelling?*
- *HOW - Without a doubt, the most important and often people talk ad infinitum about what they are going to do but never delve deep into how they are going to accomplish this. This demands a map so to speak about how you get from A to B. It also closes the loop on any thing dangling that has not been addressed. Again, a great talking point between all parties*

A CB can foster a great relationship with diverse people with diverse ideas. It also demonstrates to the client that you care about what you are delivering.”

It follows that a Creative Brief, therefore, is a TMM tool, which is Rockefeller Habit and Midas Touch compliant, from which one might fulfill or complete the circuit of the Resilient Problem Analyzer:

★ Problem Analyzer → OOPSIE⁸⁷ → Creative Brief → M.A.P.⁸⁸ → **OPSP⁸⁹**

⁸⁵ pp. 22+

⁸⁶ pp.14+

⁸⁷ Author’s proprietary deal analyzer

⁸⁸ Management Accountability Plan

⁸⁹ One-page Strategic Plan

Cash flow Circuit Theory

In the circulation of cash/currency, there are three rules that must be remembered:

1. Cash is king *but* fiat cash is trash
2. Make it easy for people to give you money (reduce impedance)
3. Money velocity is the equivalent of flux, if your cash isn't liquid, it might as well not be there. You need your "reserves" (capacitance) to be an active element in the circuit, not passive.

In the circulation of worldwide cash, there is an active concerted effort to put the power of the economy in the hands of a few - a "New World Order"⁹⁰ - and this group is ultra-powerful and elite⁹¹. One person in particular controls up to \$10 trillion in real estate assets⁹². This is, of course, a colossal mistake⁹³.

But, let us pretend that the 2018-2022+ (Agenda 2030⁹⁴) situation was not some form of parallel Universe (Twilight Zone) and life was 'normal.' That means booms and busts, surges and Great Depressions, etc. From even before the Magna Carta and advent of the roots of capitalism to now, there have always been rules to money, and its circulation and flow. Naturally, certain men have perverted it, philosophized it, and performed strange John Dee-like alchemy upon it, attempting to thwart natural order⁹⁵, or force development in places that resist development⁹⁶. But, more importantly, the current still flowed. You can damn a river, but it will still flood and flow on to the ocean.

The issue is, how do we identify the most pertinent energetic elements in a circuit, when it comes to the making of cash (increasing Top and Bottom line revenues?) We must acknowledge the basic RLC facts:

- Impedance is waste (usually costs/overhead & deadweight payroll)
- Parallel circuits divide currency, but keep tensions even
- Series circuits keep currency even, but complicate the tensions and overload the source (usually a customer base)

Think of how many companies fail when they try to exceed on a single parallel project, making it a sole priority for a company, at the expense of others? Or how many try to build a monopoly in vertical integration, only to end up pancaking themselves under bureaucratic

⁹⁰ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p_UY3YDnBIE

⁹¹ <https://www.cnbc.com/2022/04/03/a-new-world-order-is-emerging-and-the-world-is-not-ready-for-it.html>

⁹²

<https://www.cnbc.com/2022/03/24/blackrocks-larry-fink-who-oversees-10-trillion-says-russia-ukraine-war-is-ending-globalization.html>

⁹³ Allowing monopolies is always a mistake. Disney Corp. is a mistake waiting to collapse upon itself. It's already beginning to happen. They are losing families, the cornerstone of the corporation.

⁹⁴

<https://www.un.org/development/desa/jpo/wp-content/uploads/sites/55/2017/02/2030-Agenda-for-Sustainable-Development-KCSD-Primer-new.pdf>

⁹⁵ The very basis of Keynesian Economics.

⁹⁶ Africa, for example.

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weight (General Motors, anyone?). The issue is, in all three cases: how to have a strong *enough* load to 'resist' the circuit failure and an end to cash flow.

Recently a colleague and PEM cosmologist experienced this. He is recovering in that the problem - logistics supply chain collapse and the skyrocketing costs of integrated circuit chips - has fueled his desire to solve the problem with a novel approach which will be both enriching and patriotic. However, the fundamental issue is that the hardware-as-a-service business, despite not having a brick and mortar (as the author does), turned out to be just as vulnerable to the Source-Load problem as any other business. It's difficult to "own" or control a bottleneck so easily influenced by the globalization / non-linear dynamical problems, and yet controlling all chokepoints and bottlenecks are exactly the crux of issues in the "Rockefeller Habits" management method. So we see that in an elemental pursuit, we must address the fundamental issue of the analog circuit model: scalability.

In college the author was part of a team that wanted to make powerline communications possible. Great. We designed all the modules, filters, etc. But while we did each step well, and the advisors missed the most obvious and pertinent fact, which we only discovered when we came back together: once the modules were connected the **entire RLC parameters of the entire analog circuit changed**. Therefore the filters were out of range, the amplifiers were insufficient, etc. It was a complete and total failure, unlike the author's other team's project (he led) which did digital supercomputer simulation (all software). This goes back to the predictability and ease of use of digital elements, transistors, etc. The fact is that if a person, project, or management team is or acts as a potentiometer, for example, they will be a bit unpredictable in performance, day to day. People are not digital or software elements. They are the problem, but they also are the solution.

Therefore, we must consider - carefully - the formation of organizational teams and **departments** which are able to control, almost with autonomy (but also heavy accountability):

- Costs
- Payrolls
- R&D budgeting (if not allocation at least application, with liability for slip ups)
- Reward systems and incentives
- Marketing / thematics of the product or service
- Potentially, depending on circumstances, the customer interaction and servicing
- Support
- Lifespan

If the team is not mostly autonomous (not sovereign!), then after all it will be another parallel or series analog element in the cash flow circuit. That means it is its own RLC with source-load issues, rather than accepting inputs (budget constraints) and giving predictable outputs (revenues and product or service quality).

Regarding the use of departments as specialty elements, such as transformers, these are timed or limited applications. They are, in essence, only expected to behave on a limited function, or put the rest of the cash flow circuit at risk. There is no spoken or unspoken rule that a transformer department needs to be headed or even contain a true transformer. It might be that a combination of elements, with a few smartly placed switches and transistors, is able to

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approximate the same magic that a unique and rarely qualified individual will possess. This would, in theory, provide some buffer or resiliency to failure. However, there is a definite fact of life that talent is a rare quality:

★ Collect capacitors, you're going to need them in spades if you scale the business

Regarding the special role of Inductors, and how to handle their natural 'competitors': the resistors.

Inductors store current. That means within the coils of a project, department, or the knowledge and connections of a wise, experienced element of the company with all of their connections, current and future revenues may be found. You must keep these elements "happy" at all times. As currency fluctuates (alternates), impedance increases, leading to the mistaken belief that these people hate change. It isn't change, it's just that hysteresis (inertia and memory) is naturally an enemy to the alternation of the currency. An inductor is just as happy to circulate credit as cash, gold, or crypto. However, what they cannot abide is people impeding the flow of current. Resistors are natural impediments to current flow, but not directly. They create voltage/tension load and a certain amount of waste.

Let's walk through a generic or even cliché example. Nancy walks into the board meeting. Nancy is the company's best seller. Nancy is also very creative and good with people. Nancy proposes a new loyalty program that will "lock in" some of her best and most profitable clients by offering a "scratch my back, I'll scratch yours" incentive or kickback program. She is fairly sure this will give her a massive Christmas bonus and help the company bottom line. All her customers will love it. She pitches the idea and right away a Switch - a lawyer - and a Resistor - HR team manager - shoot her down.

They provide no solutions, only endless speculation about the legal issues and problems which will arise from this program, and injecting fear and poison into the discussion, sowing doubt, even making Nancy look foolish. Now the lack of predictable cash flow, not to mention the disappearing bonus she imagined in her pocket already, has her flustered. Without management's deft intervention into this high Voltage situation in the boardroom on an otherwise innocuous Casual Friday, will lead to Nancy - the company's top earner - leaving, and taking her capacitance (and client list) elsewhere. This is a crisis in the making.

It is important to recognize three things about this fictional, albeit highly believable situation.

1. Humans are unpredictable, and Nancy had no specific way of knowing how it'd be taken, nor could anyone predict she would greedily try to become a CEO in a single meeting.
2. The opportunities that exist in this impromptu exchange are **easy to miss** when fuses pop, and circuit breakers of trust, respect, and professional courtesy slam off the management circuit. Perhaps underlying this is beef between Nancy and the lawyer, and an inappropriate, undisclosed (but well known) relationship between herself and the HR manager, leading to the couple's bickering as an undertone. Perhaps Nancy is really a problematic transistor type inductor whose previous normal predictability has been compromised as her "coils" became unwound in office gossip and politics. Or, perhaps she is the victim of the Resistors! Perhaps she needs a strong transformer to back her up and pop the fuses. No matter what: subtext matters.

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3. The fundamental issue of loyalty, capacitance, and cash flow **facts** (revenues and profits) exceed the importance of all other human concerns, and yet will be quickly forgotten when egos are burned or failed to be stroked, when they absolutely should be.

If the above company had made hiring people of verbal talent and psychological capacitance their priority, instead of naysaying nags, nitpicking their way through people to create the illusion that only they have no competency ceilings and everyone else is trash... then someone could have gently guided the discussion another way. A curt "we'll put it to vote at the quarterly Board meeting" at the exact right moment would shut up all three people and curtail many issues. Too often the belief that Nancy should be quiet and "stay in her lane" will prevail because people want the elements to stay the same. But people have many capacities, not only one. Fundamentally, Nancy is an Inductor. She meets and likes people, and they like her for many obvious reasons: charm, sexual appeal, humor, grace, high EQ, charitability, etc.. However, she will see herself as high in capacitance (deserved or not), low in impedance (even though she is derailing a Casual Friday meeting at lunch), deserving of more current and yet not noticing the tension her ideas introduce. She is human, after all, and deserving of love and respect. But in a business setting, much is settled by one word: performance.

If Nancy's performance is as hot as she feels/is/believes: the circuit of cash flow will rotate about her inducing qualities. If it is not, then her directness will lead to a short circuit situation, and fuses will pop. Frankly, if her capacitance approaches 0, then no amount of alternate currency will save her charge. She will still lose that job or disqualify herself right out of it (be fired). Her own switch will turn off in the meeting and start a spiral towards circuit decay.

If Nancy is an integral circuit element, and a person of supreme importance - or a family member in a family company - this is very, very bad news for all concerned.⁹⁷

⁹⁷ *"I was a Director of corporate Films for a worldwide agency and was hired to direct and produce a Corporate Image piece focusing on a revolutionary method of open Heart Surgery. The client was Johnson & Johnson's subsidiary Ethicon Endo-Surgery, the gold standard for minimally invasive instruments as well as a Top Tier International Research Center. The name of the surgery was MIDCAB, Minimally Invasive Direct Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery. This meant all open heart surgeries would be done through ports and there would be no Heart-Lung Bypass machine.*

The Brief outlined that we would primarily approach this film in a documentary fashion, using excerpts from Heart Surgeon interviews as the soundtrack instead of a narrator reading a script. This method added authenticity to the words being spoken because they are coming from J & J's clients, not a mouthpiece for the Company.

The shooting went well, we interviewed multifarious Heart Surgeons and were able to show the client (3 men in high level positions) the work in progress. As we are wrapping and everyone is thrilled with the outcome, a new figure emerges and inserts himself into this project. This man was a French Dictator type and claimed that the creative brief was completely wrong and we needed to re-do the piece. Not one person spoke up with the exception of myself and I went toe to toe with him but in the end, we redid a beautiful piece into a product how-to. The reason behind his act is that the CEO of Ethicon needed a piece (video) that correlated to his speech he was making at an international symposium.

My client's stayed silent because they feared for their jobs. Truth was not upheld but in the end, news of this filtered to my Company's Board. The CFO and the CEO saw the original piece and thought it was the best work they had seen in a corporate environment. They went to bat for themselves really and the original piece was finally shown throughout the company and eventually J & J/Ethicon wanted it too."

~M. Asbury (female editor, EPEMC papers of the author)

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★ Manage the elements one sees, not the ones they see or expect to see.

Regarding NFTs and other tokens, Proof-of-stake as cash flow revenue hedges

One of the neat aspects of Mother Nature, and this includes the capital marketplace, is the introduction of balancing elements that attempt to create homeostasis. The Father designed the Universe to thwart the de facto existence of equality and equilibrium, but people regardless seek after it.. Instead, there is a 'sloshing' back and forth of various elements seeking after the equilibrium but never finding it. A lack of contentment is the Way to satisfaction (and vice versa) for the tough-minded manager, entrepreneur, and artist, after all. Nevertheless, as capital markets are collapsing (under the weight of a Socialist-Fascist "Axis of evil") and the shrinkage of credit and money velocity, increasing inflation,⁹⁸ and crushing home debt and a Derivatives Market of unimaginable proportions... the market has responded with new means for individuals, and therefore companies, to make money.

- ❖ Cryptocurrency
 - Including futures and options
 - Including even gambling and 'bots'
- ❖ Proof of Stake (lending)
- ❖ NFTs

Of these the corporations have really latched onto the non-fungible tokens, as if it were the new QR code for transactions, the way the UPC code changed retail and tracking. It is remarkable, and useful, to be able to see the exact ether-trail (or other crypto chain) based upon the serial codes at the end of the blockchain. It is also frightening because some of the socialists and communists, and definitely fascists want to track what people *buy* and even *say* online with token blockchain tracking. With the AI face-recognition around to persecute innocent "regular Joe's" and deep fakes to enable politicians and paid liars (celebrities, etc.) to fabricate narratives and false realities for their own propaganda and against their enemies, it makes it hard to condone anything about Web 3.0 at this point.

Nevertheless, in the grassroots of the movement, there is a growing decentralized App (dApp) community producing numerous free or cheap products, or even products which will make people money once the common consumer understands how to use them and expand the market supply & demand chain.

At this time, it isn't big money. Facebook lost big money in web 3.0, but the author doesn't think that spells the end of the story. Of course the author, and colleague A. Hardin, plans to move things right through web 3.0 towards web 4.0, to steer the course back from an evil direction towards a mimsical good. However, the forces are tremendous. That's why the use of products which do *not* use NFTs, such as the author's free Starter Grower, and the purchase of Eulium⁹⁹ coin for scientific projects, is really very important. Hopefully the reader and business people (and scientists and engineers) will consider these options. For now, the author simply

⁹⁸ Hilariously, but unfactually called Bidenflation.

⁹⁹ www.eulium.org/wp.pdf

states: be prepared to make crypto a 10-20% part of R&D and revenue streams by the 2030 mark. Start by accessing the author's crypto guide, and go from there.

Figure 15 - Starter Grower © (www.startergrower.com) and Author's proprietary Project Power Curve; credit: author/F. Dida

Socioeconomics and Geopolitics as Circuit Elements

These two broad, difficult and complex subjects are unable to be talked about without creating some tension. However, scientifically we can speak about their RLC and heat characteristics. We can also, to some degree, mimsically identify the philosophical basis for circuit elemental behavior.

Chiefly we are interested in the amplification, modulation, or attenuation of **signals** in business and market dynamics. What do we mean here? There are indicators, such as volatility, market sentiment, commodities and futures prices, indices, bonds market fluctuations, etc. which will cause the individual business 'circuit' and cash flow to be affected. This is, roughly speaking, just like the solar electric overload of a solar flare, and its downhill effect upon the Earth's internal Planetary Electric Circuit. Recently, for example there have been two CME's that were Earth directed, one was an M-class. At the same time as this CME was arriving, problems arose in the author's life which were *electronic related*, but not caused by the CME. In one case a groundhog chewed through the clinic fiber optics on a Monday (no less). In the other the car battery suddenly and without warning decided to be dead, forcing a tow situation. The

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electronics of the vehicle performed very oddly at this time, and it was as if the computer itself had died. Bear in mind there is no proof that the battery was fried by the CME (it was 5 years old or more), nor that the groundhog was influenced to seek out IT communications to lick. However, there is something rather interesting about the conjunction of the events, and others besides. Aside from their physical (and unexpected) costs, and their annoying inconveniences, the events seemed non-linear and yet, 'expected.'

Figure 16 - Space weather data for 3/28/22; credit: spaceweather.com¹⁰⁰

Something was expected. Internet communications were down, and the CME had a definite impact on human infrastructure, but how did this translate in such a bizarre and specific way? The answer is not clear.

Similarly, when market sentiment disconnects from obviousness (war, famine, catastrophe, etc.) and markets suddenly rise or fall, it may very well be that there is a non-linear nature to it. We can consider this, then, as the results in a business circuit of the analog nature of modern money mechanics¹⁰¹. That, in fact, there are multifactorial and multitudinous means whereby circuit elements lose cohesion with the environment, and yet remain circuit elements. Chaos, for lack of a better word, wins out.

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.spaceweather.com/archive.php?view=1&day=28&month=03&year=2022>

¹⁰¹ https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/4a/Modern_Money_Mechanics.pdf

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As for the heat induced by socioeconomic crises, or from geopolitics (think war, diplomacy, trade deals gone sour, etc.), it is obvious that heat affects the electronic performance of a circuit bound by materials, such as silicon, copper, plastic, etc. But these circuits we speak of are human circuits, and more to the point, probably influenced by the sudden emergence or disappearance of support of an underlying ætherial charge. If bolstered, any stupid thing, let alone great thing, seems possible. If there is no support, even what “should and could be” seems out of grasp and impossible.

Dætherially speaking, evidence for this exists in myriad product and invention launches which had some much stellar promise (Google Glass, Tesla Truck, Nintendo VR, etc.) and yet fell very flat despite all hype and human support. Many athletes with spiritual support of “John Q Public” became failures. And many with no prospects became heroes. This happens to companies a lot, and no one in the coaching or managing environment seems to want to talk about its meaning and implications. It implies that there are as yet unknown and perhaps nonlinear processes by which to attract and receive the support of an unknown (spiritual?) force, and lead the situation from zero to hero. Or without which, from hero to zero. That data is more present than ever before, for example with the Meta failure. The data is speaking volumes, and as usual, because of the fear of the heat of geopolitics and socioeconomics, it is uncommon to call it out. Mostly because “fighting words” and high circuit burnout of elements are likely to result from a worldwide circuit/system so overloaded with obvious tension and the potential for much, much more current¹⁰² (but no direct prospects of it anytime soon, only more cons and lies.)

Figure 17 - The Meta failure and Orwellian con of a fascist “hero” is instant meme territory for a company; credit: Grant Stern @grantstern

It is recommended that a “circuit element” be added: a ‘black box’ of unique power and utility in a corporate circuit (or a special, and trustworthy individual at the small and medium scale): an emergency evaluator and disaster prevention auditor (EEDPA). This person(s) would be responsible for recognizing Public Relations, market, and environmental disasters *before* they became Enron, BP/Horizons tanker, Southwest/COVID, Facebook/Meta, Microsoft phone level disasters. They could identify specific inputs and data, and then go forward with that data and make **direct action advisory to the Board of Directors and Executive team**, in the name of preventing company catastrophes that frequently happen when committees make groupthink decisions

¹⁰² The author speaks directly and indirectly of the SPACER movement, versus the War Economy, the subject of which will be an entire paper by itself.
<https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

(think Ghostbusters 2016 or Rian Johnson “Star Wars” level bad). In such cases, one needs *more IQ, TIQ, and EQ involved*, not less¹⁰³. Although, wouldn’t it be even better if it weren’t applied retroactively and reactively, but proactively?

Aether Flux and Dæther involvement in Operations Management

We do not have - and desperately do need - an anatomy for the Aether. But the proposition of a dæther is important, nevertheless, because it can be based solely upon gas and plasma physics, would provide a Numbers led form of model and testable evidence, and finally could be used in Operations and Project Management (OPM¹⁰⁴). It would, in essence, be a similar science and math (in relation) to Data Analytics. It might - probably, but who knows? - give DA a serious boost in use and utility for macro scale systems. However, nonlinear dynamics and fractal mathematics are *not* the author’s forte or in the requisite set of skills to model this.

However, this is a philosophy paper, and we have the range and authority to speculate. Firstly, the dæther might be useful in modeling the connections and bessel connections via the “Big G” diagram¹⁰⁵, probably using the Dougherty Set¹⁰⁶.

Secondly, there is a strong need because of the supply chain logistics and globalization being so out of control, one sided, and anti-mimsical (in terms of SPACERS and TED//Next^{Next} needs). We desperately need a change to our global civilization, or we shall go the way of the Pueblo, Cahokians, Mayans and countless other civilizations that failed and abandoned the endeavor. Our society will end up just as another Ur!

Therefore, here, the author promotes the idea that we should find dæthereal involvement in all of sub sciences of Operations Research:

¹⁰³ Some have called for a concatenation of all three to become a “Wisdom Quotient”. The author is in support of the spirit of this, but data wise, it might be difficult to make realistically speaking.

¹⁰⁴ Not to be confused with the author’s favorite OPM, other people’s money :)

¹⁰⁵

http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SmBD-EUwxhk&list=PLMvFffbgKgbprpVDaxns9J90yyXYBbKKy>

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| <input type="checkbox"/> Simulation | <input type="checkbox"/> Bayesian Search theory |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Linear Programming | <input type="checkbox"/> Behavioral Operations Management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Nonlinear Programming | <input type="checkbox"/> Brailsford Analysis |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering statistics | <input type="checkbox"/> Confrontation Analysis |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial engineering | <input type="checkbox"/> Drama Theory |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Management Science | <input type="checkbox"/> Knee-curve theory |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Modeling | <input type="checkbox"/> Gaming Theory |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Network Theory | <input type="checkbox"/> Six Sigma |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Production Planning | <input type="checkbox"/> VeRoLog |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Queuing Theory | <input type="checkbox"/> Uncertainty Quantification |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Computer Scheduling | <input type="checkbox"/> System dynamics |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 4OR | <input type="checkbox"/> etc. |

Operations Research and Data Analytics, the conjunction of N and P powers within a business context

There are geometries and shapes which guide physico-mechanical behaviors in reality. These are concrete realities which cannot be altered by desire, whim, or subjective force. However, if the PPC allows it, there does appear to be a quantum tunneling/shifting mechanism. Ignoring these ‘jiggles’ we can talk about linear physical reality, sans “magick” or miracles¹⁰⁷. The fact is that these hard realities are all guided by known/knowable and even predictable (to a degree of precision) factors or properties:

- Temperature
- Volume (in mols)
- Mass
- Charge
- Velocity
- Etc.

Notice that energy level is *not* on this list. Energy levels are a theory, and a clearly incomplete theory. That will remain true so long as mankind does not seek, earnestly, to understand the Unified Force - the PEM, and create the Unified Aether Field. But, that’s the subject for another paper.

In this we are interested in the hardness of the P power, and how it is mediation between the G and N powers, making it effectively the ultimate MIMS. This isn’t a theological paper, however, and discussing the whims and desires of God is not practicable. But the axial mapping between physics (natural philosophæ) and numbers (engineered into mathematics) is the subject of continual issue in the fields of cosmological physics, astronomy, and theoretical physics.

¹⁰⁷ MIMS 2.2.1.1-3; the “Threefold Sciences” (not yet published) <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

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It isn't in high energy physics; math is a tool, and empiricism is king. Why is this such an issue for the others? It should not be for astronomy, but the difficulty of studying so much, so far away, with so few tools has led to a bent for philosophy. As for the other two they are wagging the dog, and blaming one another for the cosmological crisis. In the end, the issue is moot to the Universe. Therefore, what we desire in business - concrete and predictable results - is best had by obeying physics and data. It is best, of course, if the analysis of the data is predictive in capability. But it could very well be that the predictiveness could **only** be relied upon because of physics, and that this might be the only major consideration in implementation of any managerial policy.

Which means diversity, political correctness, race and anything other than qualification and being the best for the job is **simply not good enough** and probably disrespectful to logic, empiricism, and counter to the very purpose of a business. It is not the job of a business to fix social woes. Provide solutions? Sure. Products and services which improve life are the hallmark of how capitalism fixed world poverty and provided for the ability to grow more humans while improving lifestyles and opportunities. However, all the rest, the "Social Justice Warrior" credos, are (essentially) worthless. Mother Nature herself repeatedly takes a crap upon them in market results. "Go woke, go broke," is a very appropriate if not eye-rolling response to most of the backboneless, obsequious, and largely misgiven and profit-destroying initiatives seen spreading through the market.¹⁰⁸ For now, we will simply end with this fact: just as space does not care what your credos are, neither does the marketplace and its consumers and customers. The market only respects supply/demand and the direct factors of quality and credit/liquidity that reflects the natural physics of a world where 'dog eats dog.'

The truth is that the weak of mind are worse off than the weak of body. But the weak with physics and data are weakest of all. They have no logical mind, and no ability, and are being rapidly left behind even by the changing business system they demanded. The new rules will be harsher than before because the margin for survival shrinks when the anti-MIMS, such as irrationalism and socialism, dry up all the 'fat' of businesses in a desperate attempt to pay the weak and lazy, to meet idealistic, but unrealistic virtues. It started in the very journalism sources of these bad ideas (informed via the bad 'science' from fake academia), but is already spreading to corporations "too big to fail." They are failing. They will fail. Mother Nature and her nonlinear dynamics will laugh all the more, because she has one major rule,

→ "The beatings will continue until morale improves."¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁸ It is a form of parasitism, which will be better covered in the accompanying paper, "POS Theory" the author has outlined but not yet written.

¹⁰⁹ Figure 18; credit allposters.com

Conclusion

The use of electrical physics and electronics elements and laws *might* provide a form of advantage in company Shi (positional advantage), vis-a-vis dæthereal data analytics, and an augmentation of Operations Research and Management with understanding of:

- ❖ The *A* power
- ❖ The axial conjoining of the *N* and *P* powers
 - Adjointly: a list of business and economic physical laws which can be proven

The reliance upon unimodular business management styles and systems probably makes no sense, and scalar considerations (mostly supply chain, bottlenecks, and chokepoints, and especially communications breakdowns), probably limit the ability to create all encompassing software solutions. However, if the management, board, or executive team develops a thorough understanding of how electronic elements in circuits behave, they can probably improve and prevent many massive disasters by correctly identifying personality types through chemico-energetic and electrical solutions (a hypothesis the author had previous offered in the SPACERS seminal work, "Conquering the Solar System.") This should probably be the job of the proposed EEDPA manager or department. Probably not HR.

When this is done, perhaps - just perhaps - business can become a MIMS again¹¹⁰, avoid mental aberrations from anti-MIMS (like political correctness), and survive an increasingly complex and complexity-suffering globalized economy, with geopolitical mines and traps due to the New Cold War and looming threats of World War III.¹¹¹

¹¹⁰ Who knows, maybe companies will have enough fat to build incentives programs and actually pay out pensions, and stop being sheisty liars and grifters.

¹¹¹ "To Loot a Burning House," R. Careaga, 2022
<https://www.amazon.com/dp/1643384368/ref=olp-opf-redir?aod=1>

Epilogue - Remembering the Warnings of Michael Crichton's Ian Malcom and 'chaos theory'

In "Jurassic Park" and "The Lost World," genius writer M. Crichton introduced the world to the eccentric personality of Dr. Ian Malcom, a representative of the modern quantum rebel, the chaos mathematician. In this he introduces the nonlinear issue of 'complexity theory'. Long treatises by bonafide geniuses exist elsewhere. Here we only want to showcase the diagrammatic representations, and the footnotes for each diagram, and then discuss (briefly) the facts about our world economy's crippling infrastructure.

Figures 18+ credit: M. Crichton, "Jurassic Park" & "The Lost World"

Table 1 - The Chaos Diagrams of Ian Malcolm

Jurassic Park

The Lost World

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Looking across these configurations/iterations we can see that these diagrams represent a general motion from a fractal (partially unpredictable) system to a chaotic system, with destruction of unstable elements, and a return to a highly complex, reordered system.

Our economy, to be succinct, **is in the sixth configuration**, with increasing globalization throughout:

1. Age of Exploration
2. Industrialization
3. Enlightenment/Scientific revolution
4. Nuclear Age
5. Computer Age of Information/Data
6. Internet Age
7. SPACERS?

Dr. Malcolm (Crichton) said that the internet represented this generation's "Tower of Babel" in that it could bring about our demise as, like Icarus, we fly too close to the light of the gods, and our 'wax wings' melt. Rather doomsaying. However, while most agree, they focus upon non-problems (carbon dioxide, COVID), and miss the obvious issues. Or, indeed, may be misled by a New World Order seeking to guide mankind into a fascist neo-feudal and even Satanic theocracy. Certainly they are oligarchs, and according to Chaos Theory, that is bad enough. Communism and Socialism are unable to run the world, because they take so much power and put it in the hands of few, limited individuals. Egotistically, they imagine their "mighty hands" can wield this power. In reality, the truth is that they want a Great Reset¹¹² because the balance sheets (under their control) have become so toxically negative that a derivatives meltdown will be potentially worse (economically) than a tactical nuclear war. Along with this Great Reset or "Changing World Order"¹¹³ as billionaire Ray Dalio called it is a new War Economy, a subject for another paper. The author also suspects this (and the Military Industrial Complex¹¹⁴) of fomenting the Ukraine and Eastern European situation specifically for this "fiscal stimulus."¹¹⁵

Meanwhile, our interests are not purely academic. How is a company from the size range of sole proprietor or family business to that of Toyota or a mega giant, to survive and protect itself, its employees, investors, and customers and shareholders? By taking advantage of the concepts of Shi, dæther, and Operations Research/OPM, the author predicts a potentially distinct and real advantage will emerge. That is why he has introduced the Starter Grower extension system and the Resilient Score, FREETH Score, among other facets. To provide concrete results and aims. And to do so, free of charge (technically), for the whole world. Therefore, the author suggests people to download the extension, by looking at the [Resilient Approved Extensions](#)¹¹⁶ and using it, voluntarily.

Thank you for reading this paper, and God Bless.

¹¹² <https://www.weforum.org/great-reset/>

¹¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xquam0TKMw8>

¹¹⁴ https://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/eisenhower001.asp

¹¹⁵ Heinous!

¹¹⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/resilientfirmintrasite/home>

References

1. "MIMS 2.1.1-2 : Aether, Business & Analytics; With a short reflection upon the philosophies of Ayn Rand and the concepts of Fortune as it relates to the Aether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50901241/MIMS_2_1_1_2_Aether_Business_and_Analytics_With_a_short_reflection_upon_the_philosophies_of_Ayn_Rand_and_the_concepts_of_Fortune_as_it_relates_to_the_Aether
2. "MIMS 2.1.212a - Fibonacci Pressure," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67387410/MIMS_2_1_212a_Fibonacci_Pressure
3. "MIMS 2.5.1 : Financial Velocity Addendum; A Follow-up on Interesting Developments in the N power," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50902057/MIMS_2_5_1_Financial_Velocity_Addendum_A_Follow_up_on_Interesting_Developments_in_the_N_power
4. "MIMS 2.1.212b - BTF Addendum and Financial Velocity," Academia, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67983935/MIMS_2_1_212b_BTF_Addendum_and_Financial_Velocity
5. "On the Membranous Interface of the Material and the Spiritual (from an EPEMC perspective) & Dual/Double Layer Economics... a proposed test of EPEMC's 'metallic' properties: tensile strength, malleability, durability," Academia, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability
6. "MIMS 2.1.212c - BTF Addendum and Fibonacci cycles," Academia, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/69663410/MIMS_2_1_212c_BTF_Addendum_and_Fibonacci_cycles
7. "MIMS 2.102 - In pursuit of the Daether," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether
8. "MIMS 2.1.212d - BTF Reversal manifested as predicted," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/71652320/MIMS_2_1_212d_BTF_Reversal_manifested_as_predicted
9. "EEVblog 1439 - Analysing Veritasium's Electricity Misconceptions Video." Youtube, 2021, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VQsoG45Y_00
10. "The Big Misconception About Electricity," Youtube/Veritasium, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bHlhgxav9LY>
11. "Bruce Leybourne: Geometry of Earth's Endogenous Electrical Energy -- Geophysical Evidence | EU2016," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q355Haapq-0>
12. "Arc Progression 2," Youtube/FractalEarth, 2021, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kpt5VLIM_el
13. "Arc Progression 4," Youtube/FractalEarth, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dy-4Gbrez-E>
14. "Current Sources," Electronics Tutorial, <https://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/dccircuits/current-source.html>
15. "Tactical Currency Profits," Paradigm Press, J. Rickards 2022, <https://paradigm.press/publications/tac/>
16. "Strategic Intelligence, Making The Simple Complex," Paradigm Press, J. Rickards, 2022, <https://paradigm.press/publications/awn/>
17. "Winning the New Cold War & World War 3.0," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3
18. "LISTEN: Elites Tease Our 'NEW WORLD ORDER' at Global Summit | @Glenn Beck," Youtube/Blaze Tv, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pquZ3BheelE>
19. "Glenn Beck Addresses How ESG Is Destroying our Society | @Pat Gray Unleashed," Youtube/Blaze TV, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zbkCBllol2Q>

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

20. "F.R.E.E.T.H. Score," Star Enterprises/Intrasite, <https://sites.google.com/view/star-enterprises-intrasite/spacers/freeth>
21. "Peter Principle," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Peter_principle
22. "Are Financial Institutions Using ESG Social Credit Scores to Coerce Individuals, Small Businesses?" Heartland Publications, J. Haskins, 2022, <https://www.heartland.org/publications-resources/publications/financial-institutions-are-expanding-esg-social-credit-scores-to-target-individuals-small-businesses>
23. "Five ways that ESG creates value," McKinsey Quarterly, W. Henisz, T.Koller & Robin Nuttall, 2017, <https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Business%20Functions/Strategy%20and%20Corporate%20Finance/Our%20Insights/Five%20ways%20that%20ESG%20creates%20value/Five-ways-that-ESG-creates-value.ashx>
24. "How to Calculate Your Individual ESG Score," The Impact Investor, 2022, <https://theimpactinvestor.com/calculate-individual-esg-score/>
25. "'Dark empath's': how dangerous are psychopaths and narcissists with empathy?" The Conversation, N.Heym & Alexander Sumich, 2022, <https://theconversation.com/dark-empaths-how-dangerous-are-psychopaths-and-narcissists-with-empathy-178715>
26. "Lessons From History's Most Persistent Loser – Vincent Van Gogh," Inc 42, C. Galbraith, 2018, <https://inc42.com/buzz/lessons-historys-persistent-loser-vincent-van-gogh/#:~:text=He%20was%20mentally%20ill%3B%20tried.paintings%2C%20each%20worth%20millions%20today>
27. "Mozart Died Penniless. Here's Why," Grunge.com, Frank F, 2021, <https://www.grunge.com/412714/mozart-died-penniless-heres-why/>
28. "Who stole from whom? Thomas Edison vs. Nikola Tesla," Tec Review, 2020, <https://tecreview.tec.mx/2020/03/16/en/who-stole-from-whom-thomas-edison-vs-nikola-tesla/>
29. "Life of Thomas Alva Edison," Library of Congress, <https://www.loc.gov/collections/edison-company-motion-pictures-and-sound-recordings/articles-and-essays/biography/life-of-thomas-alva-edison/>
30. "Thomas Edison's Reaction To His Factory Burning Down Shows Why He Was So Successful," Business Insider, R. Feloni, 2014, <https://www.businessinsider.com/thomas-edison-in-the-obstacle-is-the-way-2014-5>
31. "Ghost In The Machine: Edison Lost Currents War But Won A Bigger Prize That Still Helps Keep The Lights On," Ge.com, T. Kellner, 2021, <https://www.ge.com/news/reports/ghost-in-the-machine-edison-lost-currents-war-but-won-a-bigger-prize-that-still-helps-keep>
32. "Breakdown Voltage," Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Breakdown_voltage
33. "MIMS 2 Applications discussions," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions
34. "Blue Chip Stock," Investopedia, J. Chen, 2020, <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/bluechipstock.asp>
35. "Jordan Peterson explains what happened to him in NEW emotional interview with Mikhaila Peterson," Youtube/Intellectual; Dark Web, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J0CJiWxeaFc>
36. "'Something MAJOR Is About To TAKE PLACE!' Jordan Peterson," Youtube/MotivHolic, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lwJ9gY6mCc8>
37. "Jordan Peterson explains what happened to him 2020 (Depression, Clonazepam, Benzodiazepine)," Youtube/For Conservatives Only, 2020, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3ktjZih3LQ>
38. "The podcast about Joe Rogan's podcast is hugely popular," Aljazeera/ Bloomberg, L. shaw, 2022, <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2022/2/17/the-podcast-about-joe-rogans-podcast-is-hugely-popular>
39. "Valuetainment," Youtube, Patrick Bet-David, <https://www.youtube.com/c/VALUETAINMENT>

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

40. "JFK Assassination: The Truth Told by Secret Service Agent Clint Hill, Youtube/Valuetainment, 2017, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vzYwCmDDSLA&list=PLFa0bDwXvBICRNOFtfmvq_dzMkNBTI5m6
41. "John McAfee Makes Strange Predictions," Youtube/Valuetainment, 2018, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WBgFGwJA1D0>
42. "Joe Rogan Experience #1284 - Graham Hancock," Youtube, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RxmW9eizOAo>
43. "Ken Bone's Disturbing Reddit History Shows He's Not Nearly as Adorable as We Thought," Daily Beast, T. Sykes, 2017, <https://www.thedailybeast.com/ken-bones-disturbing-reddit-history-shows-hes-not-nearly-as-adorable-as-we-thought>
44. "Commander Personality ENTJ-A / ENTJ-T," 16 Personalities, <https://www.16personalities.com/entj-personality>
45. "What Is a Type A Personality?," Web MD, A. Sharma, 2021, <https://www.webmd.com/balance/what-is-a-type-a-personality>
46. "Electrical length, Wiki, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electrical_length
47. "Pierre-Marie Robitaille: Kirchhoff's Claims | EU," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, 2015, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c-Luq0fOJK8>
48. "What is Kirchhoff's Law? Blackbody and Cavity Radiation!," Youtube/Sky Scholar, 2017, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DodFojdkSIA>
49. "Kirchhoffs Circuit Law," Electronic Tutorials, Aspen Core, 2022, https://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/dccircuits/dcp_4.html
50. "Today in History: Income Tax Ruled Unconstitutional in Pollock v. Farmers Loan Trust Co.," Tax Foundation, J. Bishop-Henchman, 2013, <https://taxfoundation.org/today-history-income-tax-ruled-unconstitutional-pollock-v-farmers-loan-trust-co/>
51. "Liberty Couple Charged in \$2.8 Million Embezzlement, Check Kiting Scheme to Fund Gambling, Lavish Spending," The FBI: U.S. Attorney's Office/ Western District of Missouri, 2013, <https://archives.fbi.gov/archives/kansascity/press-releases/2013/liberty-couple-charged-in-2.8-million-embezzlement-check-kiting-scheme-to-fund-gambling-lavish-spending>
52. "What Does It Mean that Taxes Are Voluntary?" TurboTax Intuit, 2021, <https://turbotax.intuit.com/tax-tips/general/what-does-it-mean-that-taxes-are-voluntary/L5cjhVlhh>
53. "Dunning-Kruger effect," Encyclopedia Britannica, B. Duignan, 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/science/Dunning-Kruger-effect>
54. "Loser's limp," Urban Dictionary, C. McShane, 2009, <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=loser%27s%20limp>
55. "MaticFomo | I Invested in a Ponzi Scheme ! Results and Did I Lose all My Money," Youtube, B. Stritton, 2022, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W_4DZJ5MRRw
56. "Defi Roi Dapps - Ponzi Schemes?/ Stable One/Maticstaker/Maticfomo, Multimatic/Matic Heaven," Youtube/CtrlZED Crypto, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h2EmEwg9HWO>
57. "MIMS 4.01 -Morality as a Simulation of Holiness," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/66889409/MIMS_4_01_Morality_as_a_Simulation_of_Holiness
58. Tough Minded Management Summary Notes, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1nu2q-INImfKqjIEFvSfFWCXcWd2r0EvX4KkhZVrXDy0/edit#heading=h.2j68p5q0s22p>
59. "MIMS 2.7-8 : War & Government; The Rise and Fall of US Military Dominance, from an Art of War perspective, and MIMS Analysis, as well as a short discussion of the history of failures of government programs from antiquity through the Great Enlightenment," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of

EPEMC :: Philosophy
Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

[US Military Dominance from an Art of War perspective and MIMS Analysis as well as a short discussion of the history of failures of government programs from antiquity through the Great Enlightenment](#)

60. "Tough-Minded Management: Third Edition," Amazon, J. D. Batten, 2002, <https://www.amazon.com/Tough-Minded-Management-Joe-D-Batten/dp/1592441181>
61. "The Marshmallow Experiment - Instant Gratification," Youtube/FloodSanDiego, 2010, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y04WF3cSd9Q>
62. "Mastering the Rockefeller Habits," https://docs.google.com/document/d/1f3E7BTgqkJeP7_PVibNdxpMo_immeqm22wFtL9bRLjs/edit#
63. "Biden Says U.S. Must Lead New World Order: What America Needs If He's Serious," Youtube, S. Forbes, 2022, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p_UY3YDnBIE
64. "Op-ed: A new world order is emerging — and the world is not ready for it," CNBC: Opinion - Politics, F. Kempe, 2022, www.cnbc.com/2022/04/03/a-new-world-order-is-emerging-and-the-world-is-not-ready-for-it.html
65. "BlackRock's Larry Fink, who oversees \$10 trillion, says Russia-Ukraine war is ending globalization," CNBC: Markets, Y. Li, 2022, <https://www.cnbc.com/2022/03/24/blackrocks-larry-fink-who-oversees-10-trillion-says-russia-ukraine-war-is-ending-globalization.html>
66. "The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development," UNSSC Knowledge Centre for Sustainable Development, <https://www.un.org/development/desa/jpo/wp-content/uploads/sites/55/2017/02/2030-Agenda-for-Sustainable-Development-KCSD-Primer-new.pdf>
67. "The Eulium Project," Eulium Development Foundation, Col. A. J. Hardin, <https://www.eulium.org/wp.pdf>
68. "Startergrower.com," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://exodus-frontend.vercel.app/login>
69. "What's Up In Space," spaceweather.com, 2022, <https://www.spaceweather.com/archive.php?view=1&day=28&month=03&year=2022>
70. "Modern Money Mechanics," Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago, A. M. L. Goczy, 1994, https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/4a/Modern_Money_Mechanics.pdf
71. "SPACERS, LLC - "Are you a spacer? (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>
72. "Explication of the Versatility of the "Big G" diagram in MIMS 1.0," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0
73. "The Dougherty Set," Youtube, B. Dougherty, 2017, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SmBD-EUwxhk&list=PLMvFffbgKgbprpVDaxns9J90yyXYBbKKv>
74. "MIMS 2.2.1.1-3 : The Threefold Science," Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1LcH2FypSjl27RZYI8NnxqtXiHq8Ub7KsFrcRIRJ3pRE/edit#heading=h.4w083fuxm8i3>
75. "To Loot a Burning House," Amazon, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://www.amazon.com/dp/1643384368/ref=olp-opf-redir?aod=1>
76. "Resilient Extensions," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IM14nrVKC2Kvche0IE-4fR19EGM2orhv9ZN9KKBGp0U/edit>
77. "The Great Reset," World Economic Forum, 2022, <https://www.weforum.org/great-reset/>
78. "Principles for Dealing with the Changing World Order," Youtube, R. Dailo, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xquam0TKMw8>
79. "Military-Industrial Complex Speech," The Avalon Project, D. D. Eisenhower, 1961, https://avalon.law.yale.edu/20th_century/eisenhower001.asp
80. "Resilient Intrasite," Resilient Firm, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/resilientfirmintrasite/home>